

RESULTS OF EXPERIMENTAL TEST WORK ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF READING AND WRITING SKILLS OF PRESCHOOLERS

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ABSTRACT

Preschool education-education implies an individual approach to each child, respect him as a person, upbringing from the spiritually rational side, education in a way that suits the interests and needs of the child. The content and methods of preschool education recognize the formation of a child's personality as his independent personality it is of great importance that the extraction processes are organized in the environment in which they take place. After all, formed as a person, matured the Foundling recognizes himself, his own, and in the future becomes the pride of the nation, the land. In preschool institution knowledge of the physical, mental and spiritual ability that helps the child achieve success in his future life in the process, it develops in the study of the environment that surrounds us, in the cultivation of speech, listening to artistic works, drawing, building, performing physical exercises and other types of activities. In these activities, the directions are with each other harmonized-organized on the basis of integrated planning and brought in an interesting way in the form of a game.

Key words: artistic works, cheerfully repeats, creative activities, law on education, labor activities, preschool educational institution.

INTRODUCTIONS

Since the game is suitable for the natural needs and desires of the little one, the game is learning in the process cheerfully repeats the topic, mastering it with relief.

To teach children to stage and creative activities, the main purpose of the science is in preschool educational institutions to carry out staging work, to give practical knowledge and skills to guide children's creativity. Uzbekistan Creative activity on the basis of the "law on education" and "concept of preschool education" of the Republic getting right is about guiding children's creativity, manual labor activities.

The main task of the preschool educational institution is the quality of the personality of each child in a way that suits the age stage to ensure the development and careful preparation of it for the next stage of education and to ensure a positive atmosphere in the institution and it consists in creating the necessary conditions. Teaching children to stage and creative activities mission is at staging children, preparing them for acting, organizing their creative activities, manual labor, artistic

labor to awaken their interests, to form the skills and competencies generated through Labor; preschool age education and professional orientation of love for work in children; for creative exhibitions, games in children

to awaken their desire to make attributes; to familiarize themselves with the properties of materials such as paper, cardboard; to work culture training skills and skills; planning, preparation of the process of preparing items to teach the technology, save the product, draw a sketch and a photo of the draft of the items orderly work places teaching to keep; teaching children to use simple tools in the process of making objects, as well as tastes it is to get used to the formation, to save time, to work on purpose.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Creative ability is a feature that distinguishes a person from an animal. This ability gives a person not only life it can come in handy during and use it, but it can also change its appearance.

Understanding children's creativity and its specific aspects requires educators to have a lot of knowledge will. What kind of character this activity has in pedagogical art, what tools does the artist use to create an artistic image using; he should be able to answer questions about what are the stages of his creative activity.

Children in the process of going to get acquainted with the world around them in their activities, that is, in their games, drawings, clay they are reflected in their work, stories, etc. The images that children receive from the world around them in pictorial activities, they try to depict emblems in their imagination using different materials and clear shapes.

In children's creativity, at the initial stage of creative activity, there are specific character traits.

These include applying previously mastered methods of work in a new way, through new methods, the tasks ahead solubility includes active and independent participation in the expression of one's own emotions through various means.

Understanding the surrounding world in children's visual activity is not associated with creative manifestations, but with the fact that the child is working, is manifested by determining the composition of the material showing. For example: pencils and paints trace on paper they leave, Clay can be made from soft flour. For further development of pictorial activities and research this stage is of minor importance, since the child will help in this to create the embodiment of his imagination get acquainted with the material.

A child who understands that the trace that remains from the pencil represents something at his own discretion and at the suggestion of an adult trying to describe some kind of object, then the child's activity will have acquired a pictorial character. Thought in a child, is the goal and tries to manifest them. Thus, the first stage of the creative process is the emergence of thought be-is also formed in the activities of the

child. With the appearance of thought in the artist, it is usually necessary to understand the content and performance thinking about the means, it usually takes a long time for work, while in a child it is often the formation of this stage not observed. The smaller the child, the faster he tries to describe what he thinks. He still has his he cannot foresee the result of his work and the way to do it. Preconception and job planning describe it is carried out in conjunction with the process. Therefore, the content of work in the process of activities in children's creativity change cases are frequent. Details that do not apply at all to the emblems in the picture that the child is depicting can enter.

A number of pedagogical in the history of pedagogy to study the specific aspects of children's pictorial creativity and psychological research was carried out.

The role of training in the development of creative abilities in children as part of a series of visual activities is incomparable in recognition of the fact that such training is also fundamental to the formation of elements of pictorial literacy in them there is no doubt that he will put his stone.

Children are known not only for something during painting, appliqué, clay work, shearing gluing Sessions the term will be busy, but in addition to what we have already mentioned above, what is in them will develop and form:

- * skills in the field of Fine Arts are identified and formulated;
- holding a pencil, mustache, working with clay, plasticine, trimming and gluing certain objects in scissors through the small arm muscles develop;
- the child prepares to master the writing technique;
- the child will be able to distribute his attention in one place through visual activity sessions and until the end of his work learns to do, to be able to sit;
 - to observe nature, the surrounding world, to cherish it, to treat it correctly learns to be;
 - to work as a team, to be able to plan work, to be able to hear comrades and to provide mutual feedback taking into account, working qualifications are formed;
 - will have an understanding and vision of the rich cultural and spiritual heritage of our people and make them own learns to express in his work.

The ability to creativity is the goal of the Johnson on the basis of the objective laws of reality of the natural and social world and is an activity that changes according to its needs. The product of creativity is the active product of the human mind. "Preschool the main content of the "concept" defines the task of developing the individual characteristics and talents of children given.

Current research is creative in drawing preschool children, making clay and plasticize toys proved able to operate. Of course, children's creativity has its own characteristics, and adult creativity cannot meet its criteria. In the educational process, children's toy due to hearing fairy tales, seeing different pictures before making, he

begins to gradually imagine what is not part of the circle of objects that he directly perceives.

In a child, images of voluntary imagination are first formed by the verbal influence of an adult, and later they are independent of the child it can arise from thinking.

3 tasks assigned to children when children learn ways to form their artistic creative abilities we can complicate the stage. At the first stage, children are taught from them in creative activity assignments are given that require direction: the tutor (make yourself, think something, look for, like an amendment) on their instructions, children work together with an educator and show elements of creativity. In the second stage assignments are given that encourage children to work and seek for a specific purpose. Together with the child caregiver the worker begins to understand that the acquired skills can be combined and changed.

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